

MAKE A GIFT

RNA22 v2 results

Results have been computed and are shown below. If there are no results shown, it means your chosen parameters yielded no results.
 Note: The p-value represents the likelihood that the target site loci is random. That is, a lower p-value represents a greater chance that the loci contains a valid MRE

miR Name ▲	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_mir_18a_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	804	-13.10	CTACCTGCA-GCCCCGGACCTTC GATAGACGTGATCTACGTGGAAT	3.59E-2
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	128	-17.70	TCCGGA-GCAGGCTCCTGCACAGCA : : CGACCTACGTT--TGGACGTTTTGA	7.28E-2
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	2351	-15.60	AGGTGAAGCAGATCTACAAGACC : CGACCTACGTTGGACGTTTTGA	1.92E-2
hsa_mir_222_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	14	-12.20	TGGTGCTGCTGCCCTGGTGAG : : TCCTAGATGTGACCGATGACTC	2.2E-1
hsa_mir_222_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	2272	-13.80	AGCTTCTGCAC--CCAGCTGAA : : TCCTAGATGTGACCGATGACTC	2.04E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	60	-17.10	CCGGACCAGCTGCCACCAGCCT : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	1.2E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	613	-17.60	AGCA-AGCACACCCCAATCAACCT : TCGTAACGT-TGGCTAGGGTTGGA	8.95E-3
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	983	-16.00	GGTCCCAAC--ATCACCACCT : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAG-GGTTGGA	2.23E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1133	-14.20	AGTGCTACGGCGTGAGCCCAACCA : : : TCGTAACGTTG-GCTAGGGTTGGA	4.01E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1141	-14.40	GCGGT--GAGCC-CCACCAAGCT : : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	4.01E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1547	-19.30	AGC--TGCTGCACG-CCCCAGCCA : : TCGTAACGTTG-GCTAGGGTTGGA	3.79E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1576	-14.20	GGC-CCCAAGAAGAGCACCACCT : : TCGTAACGTTGGCT-AGGGTTGGA	1.1E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1915	-18.40	GGCA--GCAAGCTGTTCCAGACCC : : : TCGTAACGTTG-GCTAGGGTTGGA	3.19E-1

miR Name ▲	transcript name ◆	leftmost position of predicted target site ◆	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol) ◆	heteroduplex	p value ◆
hsa_mir_9_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	328	-14.60	CTGGACAGCAAGA--CCCAGAGC : AGTATGTCGATCTATTGGTTTCT	2.49E-1
mir_21_5p	OK120841.1 Synthetic construct HCV1146 Moderna_mRNA_1273_SARS_CoV_2 vaccine sequence	1463	-12.60	GCTACTTCCCTCTGCAGAGCTA : AGTTGTAGTCAGACTATTCGAT	1.33E-3

Please [email us](#) for questions and/or suggestions - GUI created by the [Computational Medicine Center](#) at the Sidney Kimmel Medical College of Thomas Jefferson University

